

Sidelobe Suppression and Data Compression: Exploring LFM and NLFM in Compressed Sensing for Cooperative Systems

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Abstract. This paper explores the integration of compressed sensing (CS) techniques with cooperative spectrum sensing to enhance signal recovery and sidelobe suppression in communication systems, particularly for signals such as Linear Frequency Modulation (LFM) and Nonlinear Frequency Modulation (NLFM). By leveraging Virtual Data Synthesis, the proposed framework improves the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) by a factor of $L - 1$, which significantly increases the probability of successful cooperative detection while maintaining manageable false alarm rates. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of sidelobe suppression techniques for LFM and NLFM signals, which are commonly used in radar and communication systems. Through extensive simulations, the system's ability to recover phase-frequency modulated signals under low SNR conditions is evaluated, with a focus on improving cooperative detection probability and reducing interference. The results show that the proposed approach can efficiently utilize the spectrum and mitigate interference in congested frequency bands, all while operating at reduced sampling rates. This work contributes a novel method for addressing challenges in dynamic and crowded communication environments, combining CS with cooperative detection and sidelobe suppression.

Keywords: Compressed Sensing, Cooperative detection, Signal Recovery, Virtual Data Synthesis, Signal-to-Noise Ratio, Frequency Modulation.

1 Introduction

In environments where multiple communication systems share the same frequency band, adaptive waveform design plays a critical role in reducing mutual interference. By dynamically adjusting to changing interference levels, adaptive waveforms can optimize detection performance in both cooperative and competitive communication networks. Among the most effective waveforms for such applications are Linear Frequency Modulation (LFM) and Nonlinear Frequency

Modulation (NLFM), which are widely used for their pulse compression capabilities. These waveforms enable high-range resolution without requiring an increase in peak transmit power [1].

LFM signals are particularly valued for their simplicity, Doppler tolerance, and compatibility with Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)-based processing, including matched filtering and the extraction of range and Doppler information through fast- and slow-time transforms. However, they suffer from high sidelobe levels, which can degrade performance in certain scenarios. In contrast, NLFM signals inherently suppress sidelobes, improving detection and resolution. Despite these advantages, NLFM signals come with trade-offs, including increased receiver complexity and reduced Doppler tolerance [2, 3]. These characteristics make the choice between LFM and NLFM waveforms a strategic decision, depending on the specific requirements of the communication system and the operational environment.

Due to their sparse representations, LFM and NLFM waveforms are well-suited for integration into compressed sensing (CS) frameworks, enabling efficient communication data compression and recovery while enhancing detection performance. Innovations such as multitone LFM for MIMO communication [4] and sparse frequency agile approaches [5] demonstrate CS's potential for high-resolution estimation and anti-interference capabilities.

Recent advancements include the Block Kronecker Compressed Sensing (BKCS) algorithm, which processes 2D communication data to mitigate interference, reduce clutter, and improve detection accuracy with lower resource requirements [6]. Another notable development is the Intra-Pulse Frequency-Coded FMCW (IPFC-FMCW) waveform, optimized using simulated annealing, which achieves low sidelobe levels and enhanced range estimation even under jamming conditions [7]. Previous studies on Cooperative Compressed Sensing (CCS) employed a synthetic signal with rectangular windows to represent consistent spectral activity within the occupied bands, while demonstrating the absence of activity outside these bands, effectively emphasizing the sparsity concept [8, 9]. After results validations, we move to integrating CCS with LFM and NLFM signals to extend these benefits to cooperative communication and Cognitive Radio networks (CRN), further improving communication quality, bit error rate, and interference mitigation. This synergy between LFM/NLFM waveforms, CS, and CCS provides a foundation for adaptive communication systems capable of operating efficiently in congested and contested spectral environments.

2 Waveform Generation

Binary Phase Shift Keying (BPSK), LFM, and NLFM are three fundamental waveform types widely employed in CRN, each offering distinct characteristics tailored to specific applications [10]. These waveforms can be expressed in a general form:

$$x(t) = A \cdot \cos(2\pi f_c t + \phi(t)). \quad (1)$$

where A is the amplitude, f_c is the carrier frequency, and $\phi(t)$ represents the unique phase modulation of each waveform. The phase expressions are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_{\text{BPSK}}(t) &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if binary 0,} \\ \pi, & \text{if binary 1.} \end{cases} \\ \phi_{\text{LFM}}(t) &= \pi\beta t^2, \quad \beta = \frac{\Delta f}{T}. \\ \phi_{\text{NLFM}}(t) &= \pi\beta t^2 + \alpha e^{-\gamma t^2}.\end{aligned}\tag{2}$$

where: $\beta = \frac{\Delta f}{T}$ is the chirp rate for LFM, Δf is the bandwidth, T is the pulse duration, α controls the amplitude of the Gaussian taper, and γ is the Gaussian shaping factor.

Feature	BPSK	LFM	NLFM
Sidelobe	Moderate	High	Low
Doppler Tolerance	High	High	Low
Range Resolution	Low	Moderate	High
Receiver Complexity	Low	Low	High
Spectral Efficiency	Moderate	High	Moderate

Table 1. Comparison of BPSK, LFM, and NLFM Waveforms.

Table 1 summarizes the characteristics of these waveforms, emphasizing their trade-offs in radar design and their suitability for communication and cognitive radio systems. BPSK is robust against noise, simple to implement, and spectrally efficient, making it a popular choice for communication systems, especially in low-SNR environments. However, its moderate spectral efficiency can limit data rates in bandwidth-constrained scenarios. LFM signals, with their high spectral efficiency and Doppler tolerance, are well-suited for applications requiring robust performance under dynamic channel conditions, such as vehicular or aeronautical communications [11, 12]. The simplicity of LFM's receiver design further supports its integration into cognitive radio (CR) systems, where adaptability is crucial. In this work, the authors propose a Low Probability of Intercept (LPI)-based NLFM radar waveform design approach for a Cooperative Radar-Communication System (CRCS), optimizing the waveform under power and similarity constraints to ensure LPI characteristics while maintaining target detection performance. Although NLFM waveforms are less common in communication systems due to their high receiver complexity and limited Doppler tolerance, their superior range resolution, low interference levels, and excellent sidelobe suppression make them ideal for scenarios requiring spatial precision and minimal inter-user interference [13]. These trade-offs make all three waveforms strong candidates for integration into CS frameworks, where their unique attributes can be leveraged to optimize both radar and communication performance in diverse operational scenarios.

3 Compressed Sensing and Sparse Representation

CS exploits the sparsity of signals in specific transform domains to significantly reduce the number of measurements required for accurate signal reconstruction [8]. By representing a signal \mathbf{x} with only a few non-zero coefficients in a sparse domain, CS uses a linear transformation to map the signal to its compressed form expressed as:

$$\mathbf{y} = \Phi \mathbf{x} = \Phi \Psi \mathbf{s}, \quad (3)$$

where: \mathbf{x} is the Nyquist rate signal, Ψ is the sparsifying basis, Φ is the sampling matrix, $\mathbf{A} = \Phi \Psi$ is the sensing matrix and \mathbf{y} is the compressed measurement vector [8]. In communication systems, CS typically uses wavelet transforms, Fourier transforms, or other orthogonal or overcomplete bases to sparsify the communication signals.

The Restricted Isometry Property (RIP) is a key condition for ensuring that a measurement matrix \mathbf{A} preserves the structure of sparse signals during compression [9]. The RIP guarantees that the measurement process does not distort the sparse signal, thus ensuring successful reconstruction through optimization.

Formally, a matrix \mathbf{A} satisfies the RIP of order k if there exists a constant δ_k such that for all k -sparse signals \mathbf{s} , the following condition holds:

$$(1 - \delta_k) \|\mathbf{s}\|_2^2 \leq \|\Phi \mathbf{s}\|_2^2 \leq (1 + \delta_k) \|\mathbf{s}\|_2^2. \quad (4)$$

In communication systems, the RIP condition ensures that the measurements obtained from a CS scheme (such as using LFM or NLFM waveforms) will allow accurate recovery of target information from fewer measurements [14]. The value of δ_k should be small for the RIP to hold effectively. The goal of CS is to recover the original signal \mathbf{x} from its compressed measurements \mathbf{y} . The reconstruction problem can be formulated as an optimization problem:

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{s}} \|\mathbf{s}\|_1 \quad \text{subject to} \quad \mathbf{y} = \Phi \mathbf{x}. \quad (5)$$

This formulation seeks the sparsest solution $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$ that explains the measurements \mathbf{y} . The ℓ_1 -norm is used to promote sparsity, and various algorithms, such as Basis Pursuit or Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP), are commonly used to solve this optimization problem [15].

4 System Design in CS-based communication

4.1 Cooperative Detection

In this work, we focus on the feasibility of cooperative detection using CS within two distinct configurations: *Intra Cooperation* (such as in a MIMO configuration) and *Inter operation* (such as in Passive Coherent Location radars). These configurations offer different advantages in terms of spatial diversity, resolution, and robustness to interference [16, 17]. By comparing their performance in a CS

framework (as shown in table 2), we aim to establish a baseline for future investigations. While this study primarily addresses the monostatic and limited polystatic cases, we acknowledge the significant potential of fully distributed multi-static radar networks. Therefore, the exploration of multi-static cooperative detection within a CS framework is reserved for future work, building upon the foundational analysis presented here.

Feature	Multistatic Radar	Multi Receivers
Spatial Diversity	High	Limited
Coverage Area	Wide	Limited
Robustness to Interference	High	Moderate
Accuracy (Localization)	High	Moderate
Resolution	Moderate	High
Hardware Complexity	High	Moderate
Coordination Complexity	High	Low

Table 2. Comparison of Cooperation Strategies.

4.2 Materials and Methods

In communication systems employing CS, several key parameters significantly influence system performance. These parameters include the bandwidth ($B = 40$ MHz), carrier frequency ($f_c = 2.9$ GHz), which is typical for S-band radars, sampling frequency ($f_s = B$), the number of measurements ($N = 1024$), and the compression ratio ($N/M = 4$), as determined in previous studies [8, 9] under similar conditions. Other important factors are the network size (L) and the sparsity level ($K = 68$).

Phase and frequency-modulated signals are designed for a nearly flat spectrum, optimizing power distribution, reducing interference, and enhancing resilience to noise and jamming in radar and communication systems. These parameters influence signal recovery, which is based on a structured sampling matrix and the Reduced-Set Matching Pursuit (RMP) algorithm for spectrum recovery [15]. Cooperation is facilitated through AND and average fusion rules [8] according to the purpose.

The signal utilized is a combination of BPSK, LFM, and Gaussian NLFM (the flattest spectrum), centered around f_c , as shown in Fig. 1. Figure 2 illustrates the compressed data transformation that enhances the SNR by a linear factor of $L - 1$, as discussed in [9]. The framework employs CS to identify free bands within the congested carrier frequency of similar signals and evaluate the detection performance.

Fig. 1. Different communication Waveforms.

Fig. 2. Virtual Data Synthesis.

4.3 Results and discussions

Figures 3 and 4 represent the cooperative detection probability (Q_d) and the cooperative false alarm rate (Q_f) as functions of both the SNR and the number of transmit-receive (T/R) modules. The data transformation (transparent maps with red edges) shown in Figure 2 significantly enhances the recovered support compared to the original data, as illustrated in Figure 3. Although there is a slight increase in the erroneous support portion in Figure 4, the deterioration remains within acceptable limits, in compliance with the **IEEE 802.22** CR standard, ensuring an upper limit of 5×10^{-3} .

Figures 5 and Table 3 illustrate the improvement in RMSE, indicating enhanced signal reconstruction through cooperation under low SNR conditions. The RMSE improves in both directions, as cooperation across multiple channels leads to better signal recovery. Specifically, averaging spectrums from L original channels and L virtual channels, along with one averaged channel, results in a significant reduction in RMSE, as shown in Figure 5. In contrast, real channels do not show improvement in RMSE under low SNR conditions, as seen in the transparent map. The colored map, however, demonstrates improvements when employing a set of $2L + 1$ compressed measurements.

The recovered spectrum, depicted in Figure 6, closely matches the original one at $SNR = 5dB$ and $L = 4$. This similarity is reflected in the detection performance, which directly measures the quality of reconstruction, especially since communication and spectrum sensing performance is typically evaluated based

Fig. 3. Cooperative Recovered Support.

Fig. 4. Cooperative Erronious Support.

Fig. 5. RMSE Evolution for Real and All Data.

Fig. 6. Original Versus Recovered Spectra at one-fourth Nyquist rate.

on spectral characteristics such as active frequency identification and signal energy distribution. The AND rule, used in support tracking, results in the lowest Q_f , while for better signal reconstruction, the average fusion rule is employed. This rule maintains the spectrum shape with high fidelity while reducing the amplitudes of parasitic bins caused by their random positions.

SNR (dB)	RMSE ($L = 3$)	RMSE ($L = 20$)	Improvement (%)
-20	0.208	0.186	10.58
-10	0.189	0.096	49.20

Table 3. RMSE improvement with increasing L (from 3 to 20) for different SNR values.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, this work demonstrates the efficacy of integrating CS techniques with cooperative spectrum sensing in communication systems, highlighting significant improvements in signal recovery, detection probability, and false alarm rates. By leveraging advanced data transformation methods, such as Virtual Data Synthesis, the proposed framework enhances signal quality, particularly in low SNR conditions, and ensures compliance with cognitive radio standards like IEEE 802.22. The results validate the potential of this approach for efficient spectrum utilization and interference mitigation in congested frequency bands. Future work will focus on refining the system by addressing dynamic scenarios, real-world testing, and robustness to parameter variations, ultimately advancing its deployment in complex environments.

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